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Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D4: Data Management and Ethics Handling v3.0

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Executive Summary

CODECO Deliverable D4 is the third and final version of *the CODECO Data Management and Ethics Handling (DME)* deliverable, developed under WP1, Task 1.1. It provides a complete account of the data generated, curated, and shared throughout the project lifespan (January 2023 – March 2026), updating the intermediate reporting provided in D3. As part of making research data *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable (FAIR)*, ethical dimensions of handling the data that are necessary for the use-cases, and how to correctly manage them throughout the project were considered.

Over the course of the project, the CODECO consortium produced a total of **13 open datasets** across six use-cases spanning Smart Cities and Mobility, Energy, and Manufacturing. All datasets are publicly available under CC BY 4.0 licences, assigned persistent DOIs, and deposited across three complementary repositories, hereafter referred to as the **CODECO data repositories**: the CODECO Eclipse Research GitLab, Zenodo, and figShare, ensuring redundancy and broad discoverability, including indexation via data.europa.eu and OpenAIRE. The datasets are listed in detail in Section 3 and summarized in this executive summary:

Smart Cities and Mobility ([P2 – Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility](#), i2CAT)

- HEU-101092696-CODECO-Trajectories — Private vehicle trajectory data in urban environments with collision scenarios (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19006361)
- HEU-101092696-CODECO-VRUMobility — Urban mobility patterns of Vulnerable Road Users including pedestrians, cyclists, and e-scooter riders (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19006361)

Smart Cities ([P3 – MDS across Decentralised Edge-Cloud](#), Telefonica)

- HEU-101092696-CODECO-P3-MDS-MediaConsumptionTraffic — HTTP request/response traces from video streaming sessions across a CDN-based 5G edge infrastructure (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19006500)

Energy ([P4 – Demand Side Management in Decentralised Grids](#), UPM)

- HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-A — Electricity consumption, PV generation, CO₂ intensity, and market price data, Building A, ETSIT campus (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19006030)
- HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-B — Same indicators, Building B (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19006030)
- HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-C — Same indicators, Building C (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19006030)
- HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-D — Same indicators, Building D (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19006030)

Manufacturing ([P5 – Wireless AGV Control for Flexible Factories](#), fortiss)

- HEU-101092696-CODECO-UC5-AGVTasks — AMR node status logs recording robotics infrastructure state and task assignments (DOI: 10.6084/m9.figShare.31724350)
- HEU-101092696-CODECO-UC5-AGVSensing — Edge robotics path dataset recording navigation goals, trajectories, velocity commands, and edge resource usage (DOI: 10.6084/m9.figShare.31724350)

Energy ([P6 – Smart Buildings](#), Almende)

- HEU-101092696-CODECO-ALM-0001 — High-frequency timestamped counter data from a smart building device (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19006240)
- HEU-101092696-CODECO-ALM-0002 — RSSI signal strength measurements between smart building devices over time (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19006240)

Experimentation Framework ([CODEF](#), [ATH](#) & [CSDG](#), [UPRC](#))

- HEU-101092696-CODECO-SDG — Synthetic infrastructure monitoring metrics from a Kubernetes cluster, generated by the CODECO Synthetic Data Generator (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19005424)
- HEU-101092696-CODECO-CODEF-Resources — Real-world CPU and memory utilisation time-series from Kubernetes-based cloud-edge infrastructures during CODEF benchmarking experiments (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19005332)

This final version of the DME also documents the impact of the datasets on the research and industry communities and addresses the sustainability of data access and stewardship beyond the project's end date of 31 March 2026, as required under the Horizon Europe Open Science policy.

Keywords: Cloud, Data Collection, Data Management, Edge, Ethics, FAIR, GDPR, Internet of Things, Network Technologies, Open Source, Software.

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v0.2	25.03.2026	Initial draft	Ana Solange Leal, INO
v0.3	30.03.2026	Integration of input by internal reviewers	Rute C. Sofia, FOR
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v0.5	22.04.2026	Release to the EC	Rute C. Sofia, FOR

Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Definition
ACM	Automated Configuration Management (CODECO framework component)
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMR	Automated Mobile Robot
API	Application Programming Interface
B5G	Beyond 5 th Generation (mobile networks)
CC	Creative Commons
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum
CODEF	CODECO Experimentation Framework
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSDG	CODECO Synthetic Data Generator
DCAT-AP	Data Catalogue Vocabulary Application Profile
DME	Data Management and Ethics Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
Dx	Deliverable x
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ETC	Ethics Committee
ETSIT	Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Telecomunicación
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GeA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HAR	HTTP Archive
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
IRCEP	Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme
KuDECO	Eclipse KuDECO project (open platform)
MDS	Media Delivery System
ML	Machine Learning
MDM	Metadata manager (CODECO framework component)
OSS	Open-Source Software
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised learning and Context-awareness (CODECO framework component)
PID	Persistent Identifier
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
PV	Photovoltaic
QoE	Quality of Experience
REE	Red Eléctrica de España
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SWM	Seamless Workload Migration (CODECO framework component)
UC	Use-case
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VRU	Vulnerable Road User

WP	Work Package
YAML	YAML ain't Markup Language

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We would like to thank all the partners who contributed to the development of the CODECO DME and who followed the guidelines throughout the project implementation. Special thanks to the Project Coordinator, Rute Sofia, from FOR.

1 Introduction

CODECO (Cognitive Decentralised Edge Cloud Orchestration) is a Horizon Europe project (Grant Agreement 101092696) developing an open-source, Kubernetes-pluggable framework for intelligent joint orchestration of compute, network, and data resources across the Edge-Cloud continuum, targeting next-generation smart services in B5G/6G environments.

CODECO Deliverable D4 - *Data Management and Ethics Handling (DME)* is a report detailing the management of all the data generated by the project. The deliverable has been developed in the context of WP1, Task 1.1 – Project and Data Management and provides the final update to the reporting provided in the CODECO deliverable D3 (M18). This final report covers the following aspects of CODECO's data handling:

- The transfer and deposit of data into open, accessible, trusted European data repositories following the principle: “**as open as possible, as closed as necessary**”, by considering three CODECO dataset repositories: CODECO Eclipse GitLab Research project, Zenodo CODECO community, and figShare CODECO community.
- The provision of information about any research output and other tools that can be used to repurpose, reuse, and validate the data.

In the pursuit of making research data *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable (FAIR)*, this final report explains the following aspects:

- What data has been collected, processed, and/or generated, per use-case.
- The handling, curation and preservation of research data during and after the end of the project.
- Which methodology has been and will be applied.
- What data will be shared or made openly accessible for verification and reuse, and how this will be done.
- How does the data preserve privacy and remain secure beyond the project duration.

This final version of the DME also includes the description of the main datasets that were generated and managed in the project.

1.1 Document Structure

In addition to the present section, the deliverable comprises the following sections:

- **Section 2 – Data Management Summary** provides an overview of the types of data generated in the project, the data collection methodology, data formats, roles and responsibilities, and use-case-specific data considerations.
- **Section 3 – FAIR Data** describes the FAIR methodology applied in CODECO, covering data findability, accessibility, interoperability, reuse, and the full catalogue of datasets produced.
- **Section 4 – Data Preservation, Storage, and Privacy** addresses the methodology for data curation, storage, backup, and deletion, including provisions for data destruction under GDPR Article 17.
- **Section 5 – Ethical Aspects** covers the ethical methodology and processes followed in CODECO, including the six-step PII verification process and GDPR compliance measures.

- **Section 6 – Impact Analysis and Sustainability Plan** documents the scientific, technological, societal, and open science impact of the CODECO datasets, and describes the sustainability measures in place beyond the project end date.
- **Section 7 – Limitations and Recommendations**, summarizes lessons learned and recommendations for the future curation and dataset collection.
- **Section 8 – Summary** concludes the deliverable.

1.2 Dependencies

D4 corresponds to the DME and covers data management and ethical aspects. Relevant deliverables that relate to D4 are:

- D1: CODECO Handbook and Gender-Neutral Guidelines **Error! Reference source not found..**
- D2: Data Management and Ethics Handling v1.0 **Error! Reference source not found..**
- D5: Risk Assessment and Management Plan, M3 [3]
- D21: Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan [4].
- D29: Lifetime Exploitation Activities [5].
- D8: Fine-grained Use-case Design and Business Impact [6].

2 Data Management Summary

2.1 Types of Data

Different types of data were collected, generated, and processed in the CODECO project as summarized in Table 1. These are described as follows:

- **Project Management and Coordination data:** data used internally in the management of the project, including minutes, project reports, financial and progress reports, as well as partners' contact list and project deliverables (public and sensitive).
- **Experimental data:** data concerning the use-case pilots, including its processing and aggregation results on the edge and communication metadata.
- **Research data:** data used to develop CODECO technologies, such as surrogate datasets used to train *Machine Learning (ML)* algorithms.
- **Derived data:** data resulting from the processing and analysis of data collected in the project, both at the Edge-Cloud, as well as processed data and curated databases with the partners.
- **Source code:** CODECO assets comprise, among others, open-source code that is publicly available via the CODECO ECL GitLab research project. This code is subject to review, updates, and overall source-code management rules. Although it is not considered directly “Data”, it is effectively the result of the work carried out in this project and needs to be placed here for consistency and discussed where deemed necessary.
- **Engagement data:** data resulting from the implementation of the *Innovation and Research Community Engagement Program - IRCEP (WP7)*.

Table 1: Categories of datasets generated in CODECO.

Data set	Examples	WP
Project management and coordination data	Project reports, GeA meeting minutes, financial and progress reports	WP1
Experimental data	Data from use-cases and from the IRCEP	WP3, WP4, WP5, WP7

Research data	Data used for the development and validation of CODECO technologies	WP3, WP4, WP5 ¹
Derived data	Scientific publications, white papers, presentations, videos	WP3, WP4, WP5, WP7
Source code	CODECO toolkits and components; CODECO Apps developed for use-cases	WP3, WP4, WP5
Engagement data	Outputs and datasets derived from IRCEP and from additional cooperative and interaction meetings	WP6, WP7

2.2 Data Collection

At the **first level of the project**, data collection encompassed primarily project management-related material, including meeting records, work and visit plans, venues, and dates, alongside architecture and framework documentation with versioning and traceability. It further included meeting minutes and protocols (with participant lists) and project reports and deliverables. As this data was intended chiefly to support internal project operations, it was stored in the internal CODECO repository hosted by FOR. Where relevant, data was made publicly available through the CODECO Zenodo community.

At the **second level**, data collection corresponded to source code development. All *Open-Source Software (OSS)* was collected, updated, and documented via the CODECO Eclipse GitLab Research project.

At the **third level**, data was collected from various cyber-physical systems, for instance, as input to use cases, including sensor and energy system data, and organised into datasets per use case. This encompassed raw data and semi-processed data from sources such as sensors and cameras, which required processing for the removal of directly and indirectly personally identifiable information (PII) prior to storage. This data was handled within CODECO under WP5 and curated via WP1 by a dedicated team as described in section 2.3, in accordance with the ethical processes described in Sections 4 and 6.

At the **fourth level**, derived data was generated from the collected experimental data. This comprised scientific and analytical outputs resulting from the execution of the source code (second level) on the cyber-physical system data (third level). Such data was captured through deliverables, reports, and scientific publications, all of which were stored in the CODECO Zenodo community.

All datasets produced in the project have an attributed DOI and were released via the CODECO datasets repositories:

- the CODECO Eclipse GitLab Research project under *datasets*¹.
- the CODECO Zenodo community, under the *datasets* category².
- figShare³.

To support consistent and uniform data collection across project partners, specifically about datasets, a standardised template was provided, comprising the following elements:

- **Dataset name:** A descriptive name for the dataset.
- **Dataset unique ID:** A unique identifier for the dataset based on a naming convention. To ensure uniqueness, the id was preceded with the prefix “HEU-101092696-CODECO”.
- **Dataset description:** A short but comprehensive description of the dataset.
- **Related WP/Task:** The Work Packages (WPs) or tasks of the CODECO workplan that are responsible for generating the dataset.

¹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/datasets>

² https://zenodo.org/communities/he-codeco/records?q=&f=resource_type%3Adataset&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

³ <https://figshare.com/search?q=codeco>

- **Data origin:** Information about the activity and actor producing the data.
- **Reuse of existing data:** This indicates whether the dataset is produced based on existing data. It also explains the mechanisms (e.g., type of processing) that enable the production of the dataset.
- **Methodologies for data collection / generation:** It illustrates the methodologies of data collection and production.
- **Data format:** The format of the dataset (e.g., CSV, JSON, PDF).
- **Data storage:** Information about where and how the dataset is stored. This may include storage of the dataset in some open access repository, like Zenodo.
- **Expected size of the data:** An estimate of the volume of data in the dataset.
- **Metadata and standards:** A list of metadata formats and/or related standards that are used in the representation of the dataset.
- **Target stakeholders:** An indication of the stakeholder groups that could benefit from access and use of the dataset.
- **Data access, sharing and licensing:** Information about the licenses of the dataset (e.g., Creative Commons – CC), as well as information about how to access and share the data (e.g., Application Programming Interfaces – APIs).

2.3 Roles and Responsibilities

CODECO had a hierarchical Data management structure, where INO represented the Project Data Manager (Ana Solange Leal), assisting the Coordinator (FOR, Rute C. Sofia) in the overall data management. All CODECO Partners were involved and were responsible, in one way or another, in data management (WP1, T1.1), playing a major role in ensuring that the data management provisions were applied. 2 provides a summary of the data processes and the responsible roles and persons, as implemented throughout the project lifespan.

Table 2: Responsible Partner Organizations and Persons.

Data Processes	Responsible	Partner and Main Person
Collection and curation of data in use-cases	Pilot/use-case Leaders	P1: UGOE, Xiaoming Fu P2: i2CAT, Jordi Marias Parella P3: TID, Luis Contreras P4: UPM, David Jimenez P5: FOR, Rute C. Sofia P6: ALM, Andries Stam
Processing and preservation of data across CODECO	Leader of WP1 and WP6 + Project Data Manager	FOR: Rute C. Sofia INO: Ana Solange Leal UGOE: Xiaoming Fu
Publishing and sharing data	Pilot/use-case Leaders, Data Owners	P2: i2CAT, Rizkallah Touma P3: TID, Luis Contreras P4: UPM, David Jimenez P5: FOR, Rute C. Sofia P6: ALM, Andries Stam
DME creation and updates	Project Data Manager	INO: Ana Solange Leal

2.4 Data Formats

Data formats are described in The CODECO project produced a total of 13 datasets, stored across the CODECO repositories as detailed in Tables 4 to 9.

Table 4 Table 3. These encompassed widely used formats such as MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx, .csv), MS Word (.docx), MS PowerPoint (.ppt), image files (.jpeg, .TIFF), among others. Most files are small (< 1GB).

Table 3: Data formats used in CODECO.

Type	Formats Used
Project management and coordination data	Based on the project templates: Word, docx, Excel, xlsx, ppt, open document odt.
Experimental data	Sensor descriptions: WoT TD; YAML; YANG
Derived data	Latex for scientific publications; word for communication
Source code	Markdown for code documentation
Outputs from IRCEP	Based on the project templates: Word, docx, Excel, xlsx, csv, ppt, xml

2.5 Use-Cases Data Overview

The CODECO key technological blocks were explored via the use of six *use-cases (UCs)*, which served as a basis for experimentation and demonstrations across three different European competitiveness markets: Smart Cities, Energy, and Manufacturing. Each partner leading a UC is its own Data Manager, being responsible for the data management on the specific UC. A specific team member oversees data gathering and quality management, aligned with WP1. In this section, considerations concerning data aspects are made for each use-case. For all use-cases involving camera, sensor, or user-interaction data, PII — including faces and vehicle licence plates — was removed or obfuscated prior to publication. The anonymisation procedures and consent processes applied are described in detail in Sections 4.1 and 5.2.

2.5.1 Smart Cities and Mobility

P1 – Smart Monitoring of the Public Infrastructure – led by UGOE. It entailed smart monitoring of Göttingen’s public infrastructure by integrating CODECO in mobile Edge nodes across the city. No dataset resulted from this UC.

P2 – Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility – led by I2CAT. P2 main concept relates to how the CODECO framework can support the deployment of vehicular digital twin services to enhance the safety of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU) in urban environments. This UC led to two (2) datasets: HEU-101092696-CODECO-Trajectories and HEU-101092696-CODECO-VRUMobility.

P3 – MDS across Decentralised Edge-Cloud – led by TID. It focused on the smart and efficient distribution of media content services across a multi-domain and resulted in one (1) dataset HEU-101092696-CODECO-P3-MDS-MediaConsumptionTraffic.

2.5.2 Energy

P4 – Demand Side Management in Decentralised Grids – led by UPM. It focused on the deployment of Edge-based Smart Energy Nodes for controlling and adjusting energy in real time, generating four (4) datasets: HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-A; HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-B; HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-C; and HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-D.

P6 – Smart Buildings – led by ALM. It applied CODECO technologies to their Crownstone smart buildings solution, resulting in two (2) datasets: HEU-101092696-CODECO-ALM-0001 and HEU-101092696-CODECO-ALM-0002.

2.5.3 Manufacturing

P5 – Wireless AGV control for flexible factories – led by FOR. It focused on the optimization of the overall efficiency of Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) and resulted in two (2) datasets: HEU-101092696-CODECO-UC5-AGVTasks and HEU-101092696-CODECO-UC5-AGVSensing.

3 FAIR Data Management and Open Science

3.1 Findability and Open Accessibility

CODECO follows a FAIR and open data sharing policy. The project addressed data following the FAIR methodology in its ecosystem, including different use-cases and training resources. The specific data privacy and management aspects are therefore aligned with the policies of the respective end-user sites. To maximize the impact of CODECO research data, the results are shared both within and beyond the consortium.

Selected data and results are openly available and shared with the CODECO stakeholders and with the broad scientific and industry communities via the CODECO Zenodo community, the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab research project and figShare, with DOIs generated in Zenodo, and is therefore accessible via data.europa.eu⁴. Data was also shared through IRCEP events, industrial workshops, and the CODECO Hackathon, targeting both research and industry communities.. For each dataset stored in Eclipse, its metadata is recorded in a text file (e.g., a readme file) to serve as support for data interpretation and deposited together with the data to describe. In line with the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement requirements, all metadata records include EU and project attribution, the grant number, publication date, embargo status where applicable, and a persistent identifier (DOI):

- “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon Europe”.
- the name of the action, acronym, and grant number.
- the publication date and the length of the embargo period, if applicable.
- a persistent and unique identifier (such as DOIs).

Files are being deposited under closed, open, or embargoed access. In case some data has an embargo status, the date for the embargo is provided, and the repository will restrict access to the data until the end of the embargo period, at which time, the content will become publicly available automatically. Project outputs, including oral presentations, posters, and scientific publications (e.g., scientific papers and book chapters), are also shared via the CODECO Zenodo community after an embargo period, if applicable.

CODECO assets that are software-based, i.e., all code and Intellectual Property contributions, followed the good practice for the development of OSS, guided by partner Eclipse in WP7 and deriving in Eclipse KuDECO⁵.

The CODECO Website is linked to both Zenodo Community and CODECO Research Labs, allowing visitors to access updated information about available resources in these repositories. Social media channels of the project were also used to inform stakeholders about the availability of a new asset or resource.

⁴ <https://data.europa.eu/data/datasets?locale=en&query=codeco&page=1>

⁵ <https://projects.eclipse.org/proposals/eclipse-kudeco>

3.2 Interoperability

All datasets use standardized formats for accessibility and ease of sharing, and the same applies to metadata. Each dataset stored is accompanied by a standardised metadata file (typically a README), recording the dataset name, unique persistent identifier description, related work packages, data format, storage location, and licensing terms. Open formats, such as YAML, are the preferred ones for configuration and metadata, consistent with Kubernetes conventions and recommendations (open documentation, open formats, and open-source code), enabling seamless use of datasets within any Kubernetes-compatible infrastructure.

All CODECO datasets were assigned DOIs, providing globally unique, persistent, and resolvable references that are a prerequisite for citation, cross-linking, and long-term interoperability.

3.3 Data Reuse

Built on an Open Science practice, CODECO's open ecosystem entailed models for co-creation, specification and validation of the research. Since an early stage (M6), CODECO provided open results (e.g., datasets, software, scientific publications) to the research and industry communities through the defined open use-cases (see section 2.5) and the offering of OSS stored on the CODECO Research Labs. During the project, all open results have been made available simultaneously across three complementary repositories - the CODECO Eclipse Research Labs, Zenodo, and figShare, ensuring that different communities, whether from open science, software engineering, or general research backgrounds, could access the same data through the platform of their preference. This approach was adopted to enhance interest, foster reusability of CODECO features and maximize impact. Business-friendly licences were applied to the OSS results, and datasets were assigned a CC BY4.0 license.

3.4 Dataset Catalogue

The CODECO project produced a total of 13 datasets, stored across the CODECO repositories as detailed in Tables 4 to 9.

Table 4: Datasets related to P2 - Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility

Dataset name	Mobility Datasets
Dataset description and PID	<p>This repository holds the two (2) mobility datasets produced within the CODECO P2 Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility, which focuses on improving road safety in urban environments using digital twins, Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications, and ML-based risk detection.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private Vehicle Trajectory on an Urban Environment with Collisions: contains simulated trajectory records of private passenger vehicles operating in an urban environment under reckless driving conditions, designed to maximise the likelihood of lateral and frontal vehicle collisions (HEU-101092696-CODECO-Trajectories) • Urban Environment Mobility Patterns with VRUs: contains trajectory and mobility records of VRUs, including pedestrians, cyclists, and electric scooter riders, as well as motor vehicles (HEU-101092696-CODECO-VRUMobility)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19006361
Repositories	CODECO Eclipse Research Gitlab (link), Zenodo (link), figShare (link)

Table 5: Datasets related to P3 - MDS across Decentralised Edge-Cloud

Dataset name	MDS Media Consumption Traffic for Edge-Cloud Video Streaming
Dataset description and PID	This dataset contains HTTP request/response traces generated during video streaming sessions in the context of the CODECO P3 - MDS across Decentralised Edge-Cloud. The data was extracted from HAR (HTTP Archive) network captures obtained from browser developer tools during demonstrations with CDN (Content Delivery Network) platform (PID: HEU-101092696-CODECO-P3-MDS-MediaConsumptionTraffic).
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19006500
Repositories	CODECO Eclipse Research Gitlab (link), Zenodo (link), figShare (link)

Table 6: Datasets related to P4 - Demand Side Management in Decentralised Grids

Dataset name	Energy Demand Management
Dataset description and PID	<p>This repository contains energy monitoring datasets generated within the CODECO P4 - Demand Side Management in Decentralised Grids and collected at the Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Telecomunicación (ETSIT) of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM). The datasets include building-level electricity consumption, photovoltaic generation, CO₂ intensity of electricity generation, electricity market prices, and solar generation forecasts.</p> <p>The monitoring infrastructure covers four buildings of the ETSIT campus, resulting in a dataset for each, as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building A: HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-A • Building B: HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-B • Building C: HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-C • Building D: HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-D <p>The repository also includes external energy-related datasets from the Spanish electricity system obtained via the Red Eléctrica de España (REE) public API, namely: <i>CO₂ Generation Intensity</i>, <i>Electricity Market Prices</i>, <i>Solar Generation Forecast</i>.</p>
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19006030
Repositories	CODECO Eclipse Research Gitlab (link), Zenodo (link), figShare (link)

Table 7: Datasets related to P5 - Wireless AGV control for flexible factories

Dataset name	AMR Manufacturing Datasets
Dataset description and PID	<p>This repository contains two (2) datasets collected from the CODECO P5 - Wireless AGV control for flexible factories, within the Automated Mobile Robot (AMR) Manufacturing testbed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AMR Node Status Logs: records the state of the robotics infrastructure and robots over time (PID: HEU-101092696-CODECO-UC5-AGVTasks) • Edge Robotics Path Dataset: records navigation goals, robot trajectory information, velocity commands, obstacle proximity, and system resource usage (PID: HEU-101092696-CODECO-UC5-AGVSensing)
DOI	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figShare.31724350
Repositories	CODECO Eclipse Research Gitlab (link), Zenodo (link), figShare (link)

Table 8: Datasets related to P6 – Smart Buildings

Dataset name	Energy-SmartBuildings
Dataset description and PID	<p>This repository contains two (2) datasets used for smart building energy and sensing experiments within the CODECO P6 – Smart Buildings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple Timer Data: contains high-frequency timestamped counter data collected from a single device (HEU-101092696-CODECO-ALM-0001) • RSSI Data: contains received signal strength indicator (RSSI) measurements between devices over time (HEU-101092696-CODECO-ALM-0002).
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19006240
Repositories	CODECO Eclipse Research Gitlab (link), Zenodo (link), figShare (link)

Table 9: Datasets related to CEI infrastructure.

Dataset name	Synthetic Infrastructure Metrics Dataset
Dataset description and PID	<p>This dataset contains synthetic infrastructure monitoring metrics collected from a Kubernetes cluster environment. The dataset was produced using a CODECO Synthetic Data Generator (CSDG) that periodically extracts metrics that simulate the behavior of the data derived from the different CODECO components of the CODECO platform (PID: HEU-101092696-CODECO-SDG).</p>
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19005424
Repositories	CODECO Research Labs (link), Zenodo (link), figShare (link)
Dataset name	CODEF Dynamic Cloud–Edge Resource Demand Dataset
Dataset description and PID	<p>This dataset contains real-world time-series measurements of CPU and memory utilisation collected from Kubernetes-based cloud–edge infrastructures during controlled benchmarking experiments conducted with the CODEF experimentation framework (PID: HEU-101092696-CODECO-CODEF-Resources).</p>
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19005332
Repositories	CODECO Eclipse Research Gitlab (link), Zenodo (link), figShare (link)

4 Data Preservation, Storage, Privacy

4.1 Data Curation

Data curation in CODECO was provided by three partners: INO (Data Manager), UGOE (Dissemination and Communication lead), and FOR (Coordinator). Curation was applied across all four data levels as follows:

First level (project management data) was preserved internally by WP1 and WP6. This data is not shared with third parties beyond mandatory reporting obligations. Deliverables and scientific publications were assigned DOIs and linked to the project website via the CODECO Zenodo community.

Second level (source code) was preserved and versioned via the CODECO Eclipse Research GitLab.

Third level (use-case and sensor data) was anonymised prior to open publication, with all personally identifiable features — including faces and vehicle licence plates — removed or obfuscated. Datasets were then stored in the CODECO repositories.

Fourth level (derived outputs: publications, reports, presentations) was made available via the CODECO website, Zenodo, figShare, and the Eclipse Research GitLab.

4.2 Data Storage and Backup

All data described in this report has been stored and controlled by the CODECO Coordinator (FOR) and the INO management team (INO). Additionally, partners were recommended throughout the course of the action to store their necessary work data locally at all four levels described in section 2.2. and summarized in section 4.1.

4.3 Data Selection and Preservation

Most data produced at the CODECO second, and third levels relate to open-source code and therefore is a primary outcome of the project. This data has significant value for the broader research community. The code and associated data preserved in the CODECO Eclipse GitLab Research Labs and KuDECO are structured to support reproducibility, with documented dependencies and versioned releases ensuring that project results can be independently validated beyond the project end date.

4.4 Data Destruction

Different levels of data in CODECO are expected to live after the project lifetime.

However, there may be cases where data expires, or one of the Partners (or external participants in the data collection) requests deletion of the data in accordance with Article 17 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which concerns the *Right to Erasure / Right to be Forgotten*. In this case, the data responsible entity will handle a secure deletion process after consultation with the CODECO Project Data Manager (INO) and the CODECO Coordinator (FOR). For this process, CODECO shall consider secure data erasure methods (e.g., specific software), ensuring that the deleted data will not be recoverable after destruction.

5 Ethical Aspects

CODECO relies on aspects related to Artificial Intelligence (AI) (such as governance and resilience) and handles diverse datasets. Therefore, ethical aspects may arise about data privacy, potential infringement of human rights, personal data collection, and misuse of developed technologies. Several activities within WP1, WP5 and WP6 addressed ethical aspects in CODECO, particularly those concerning security, information sensitivity and other ethical concerns regarding collected data and conducted research.

The data collected during the CODECO project was handled in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable European, international, and national laws on ethical principles. CODECO data is not subject to specific legal requirements and will be shared after any applicable embargo period. No dataset containing confidential information or raising any ethical or legal issues has been deposited.

5.1 Ethics Review Process

The overall process for Ethical and Security assessment is described in the CODECO handbook (D1) and was revised annually. The CODECO *Executive Board (EB)*, together with the CODECO internal *Ethics Committee (ETC)*, followed the processes as proposed in the DME (D2), ensuring that partners followed the proposed rules and complied with the legal regulations in the countries where the research was being carried out, as well as with the European Commission (EC) Ethical Legislation. For AI, CODECO implemented a specific AI governance and resilience methodology developed in WP5 - *Experimentation Framework*,

Demonstrations and AI Data Governance and Resilience Testing - that entailed verifications across CODECO use-cases and technological components [7]⁶.

The ETC was coordinated by the Project Data Manager, INO (Ana Solange Leal), integrating also ECL (Marco Jahn), the partner responsible for Open-source ecosystem coordination, and IBM (Luis Garces-Erice), the partner in charge of data observability. This Committee handled the revision of the datasets provided by partners, ensuring alignment with D2, and ensured that the GA aspects concerning Ethics were adequately followed.

The dataset verification process involved six steps (Table 10), and its execution was the responsibility of the entity owning the data, as listed in Table 3.

Table 10: Datasets Verification Process

STEP	Process	Responsible
1	Identify the dataset that is relevant	Developer of the Partner working with the dataset
2	Verify if there is any PII present ⁷	
3	Remove PII	
4	Request an additional verification of the data by a responsible from a different organization in the consortium	Developer of the organization working with the dataset asks for a second opinion to confirm all PII was removed from the dataset
5	Verify compliance, any other potential ethical issues and bias	ETC
6	Final verification of compliance and publication	Controller of Data

5.2 GDPR Compliance

The consortium committed to conducting the project in accordance with any applicable local laws, such as the GDPR 2016/679. To ensure GDPR compliance, no data was collected or used without the explicit informed consent of the subjects (e.g., users) involved. In this direction, users/subjects provided data through a properly signed informed consent form, which made explicit who would have access to the collected data, as well as for how long the data would be securely stored and subsequently deleted.

6 Impact Analysis and Sustainability Plan

This section documents the impact of the CODECO datasets and data management practices across three dimensions: scientific, technological, and societal and sectoral. Open science outcomes are addressed in Section 3. Sustainability measures covering repository continuity and community stewardship are described in Section 6.4.

6.1 Qualitative Impact

6.1.1 Scientific Impact

The 13 CODECO datasets collectively provide the research community with empirically grounded, multi-domain benchmarking resources for CEI application orchestration — a field that has historically relied on synthetic or proprietary data. The availability of real-world operational data from heterogeneous vertical domains (urban mobility, energy management,

⁶ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/carg>

⁷ CODECO consortium adhered to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data (which repealed Directive 95/46/EC), which includes any information on the dataset or metadata that includes information capable of identifying a person via an ID number, or factors specific to physical, physiological, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity.

media streaming, and factory automation) enables reproducible research and meaningful cross-domain comparisons. Several scientific publications produced within the project were validated using, or directly derived from, CODECO datasets:

- The INFRA-BENCH and CODEF datasets (HEU-101092696-CODECO-CODEF-Resources and HEU-101092696-CODECO-SDG) supported the evaluation of scheduling, workload migration, and anomaly detection algorithms published at IEEE INFOCOM 2024, IEEE ISCC 2024, and in *IEEE Access* (DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3406861).
- The Mobility datasets (HEU-101092696-CODECO-Trajectories and HEU-101092696-CODECO-VRUMobility) provide a reference dataset for vehicular digital twin research and V2X-based VRU safety services, an area with growing regulatory and standardisation relevance in Europe.
- The Energy datasets from UPM (HEU-101092696-CODECO-EnergyConsumptionUPM-A through -D) offer building-level electricity consumption, PV generation, CO₂ intensity, and market price time-series for four campus buildings — a combination of indicators rarely available together in open repositories, enabling demand-side management research grounded in real grid conditions.

The assignment of persistent DOIs to all 13 datasets through Zenodo ensures that future publications citing CODECO data are unambiguously traceable, facilitating systematic impact tracking through citation databases and OpenAIRE analytics.

6.1.2 Technological Impact

The CODECO datasets served a dual technological purpose: they were the empirical foundation for training and validating the five core components of the CODECO framework (ACM, SWM, PDLC, NetMA, MDM), and they constitute open benchmark resources that third-party developers can use to evaluate alternative orchestration solutions.

The integration of CODECO datasets into the **Eclipse KuDECO** open-source project ensures that the data is not divorced from its software context. Developers adopting KuDECO components receive, alongside the software, reference datasets and documented experimental configurations that reduce the barrier to entry for reproducible research and rapid prototyping.

The **CODEF** dataset (HEU-101092696-CODECO-CODEF-Resources) and the **Synthetic Infrastructure Metrics Dataset** (HEU-101092696-CODECO-SDG) are particularly valuable for the technological community because they provide Kubernetes-native infrastructure telemetry, e.g., CPU, memory, and proposed CODECO metrics utilisation across cloud-edge nodes during controlled benchmarking experiments, in a format directly consumable by orchestration research tools and simulation environments. These datasets are among the first of their kind to be openly released for CEI Kubernetes research.

6.1.3 Societal and Sectoral Impact

The CODECO datasets have direct relevance to the policy and operational communities in each of the three vertical markets addressed by the project.

Smart Cities and Mobility. The Mobility datasets (P2, i2CAT) document simulated and real-world urban trajectory patterns for VRUs including pedestrians, cyclists, and electric scooter riders, alongside private vehicle trajectories under collision-risk conditions. These datasets directly support the development and regulatory validation of safety services for connected urban mobility infrastructure, a domain actively addressed by EU policy frameworks including the Intelligent Transport Systems Directive and the Vehicle General Safety Regulation. The MDS dataset (P3, Telefonica) provides HTTP-level media consumption traces collected from

CDN-based video streaming in a real 5G edge deployment, supporting research into QoE-optimised content delivery that reduces network congestion and improves user experience.

Energy. The UPM energy datasets (P4) and Smart Buildings datasets (P6, Almende) collectively contribute empirical data to the EU's clean energy transition agenda. The UPM datasets encompass four campus buildings with diverse consumption profiles, PV generation, CO₂ intensity signals from the Spanish grid operator (Red Eléctrica de España), and real-time electricity market prices — enabling research into demand-response and grid-edge optimisation under realistic European energy market conditions. The Smart Buildings datasets (HEU-101092696-CODECO-ALM-0001 and -0002) provide timer and RSSI data from Crownstone smart building deployments, supporting research into low-power indoor localisation and energy-aware automation that is directly applicable to the EU's building renovation targets under the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive.

Manufacturing. The AGV/AMR datasets (P5, fortiss) contribute to the evidence base for AI-driven flexible factory automation, supporting the EU's Industry 4.0 competitiveness agenda. By providing open, labelled telemetry from a real robotic testbed — covering navigation trajectories, obstacle proximity, velocity commands, and edge compute resource usage — these datasets lower the cost for SMEs and researchers to develop and benchmark edge AI solutions for manufacturing without requiring access to a physical testbed.

6.2 Quantitative Impact

The impact of the CODECO project's data outputs can be assessed against a concrete set of measurable indicators spanning research outputs, dataset reach, multi-domain coverage, and open science compliance. The 13 CODECO datasets were published first in the Eclipse GitLab in M18, and have then been revised in M24, M38. The replication in Zenodo and figShare was done in March 2026, at the close of the project. As newly deposited records, their Zenodo view and download statistics are at an early baseline stage; meaningful longitudinal impact metrics are expected to accumulate from mid-2026 onwards. The consortium recommends that usage statistics are reviewed at three-month and twelve-month intervals post-publication through Zenodo's built-in analytics and OpenAIRE tracking, and that findings are reported through the Eclipse KuDECO community channels. The current figures, extracted in April 2026, are presented in Table 11.

Table 11: CODECO Datasets in Zenodo, verified early engagement.

Record	Title	Views		Downloads	
		Zenodo ⁸	figShare ⁹	Zenodo ⁸	figShare ⁹
19006361	Mobility Datasets (P2 – VRU + Trajectories)	29	3	33	—
19006500	MDS Media Consumption Traffic (P3)	32	8	42	—
19006030	Energy Demand Management (P4 – UPM)	46	42	54	—
19694579	AMR Manufacturing Datasets (P5)	<i>Too new — not yet indexed</i>	—	46	—
19006240	Energy – Smart Buildings (P6 – Almende)	50	30	54	—

⁸ Since March 2026.

⁹ Since March 2026.

Record	Title	Views		Downloads	
		Zenodo ⁸	figShare ⁹	Zenodo ⁸	figShare ⁹
19005424	Synthetic Infrastructure Metrics – CSDG	30	16	49	—
19005332	CODEF Dynamic Cloud-Edge Resource Demand	38	9	47	—

6.3 Sustainability Plan

6.3.1 Repository and Dataset Continuity

All CODECO datasets are preserved in repositories with institutional guarantees of long-term availability:

- **Zenodo**, operated by CERN under OpenAIRE EU support, offers indefinite data preservation with a commitment to maintain access even if the repository service model changes, in accordance with its data policy.
- **figShare**, operated by Digital Science, provides persistent DOIs and long-term storage with redundant backups.
- **CODECO Eclipse Research GitLab** is governed by the Eclipse Foundation, an independent not-for-profit organisation. The dataset repositories are archived under the **Eclipse KuDECO** project namespace, which continues as an active open-source project beyond the CODECO grant period, ensuring that the datasets remain integrated with a living software ecosystem and discoverable to the developer community.

No active hosting cost is required beyond the project end date: all three platforms provide free, perpetual access for open-access deposits.

6.3.2 Community Stewardship

The transition from CODECO as a time-limited project to a sustainable community resource is anchored in the Eclipse KuDECO open-source project, which assumes stewardship of the CODECO framework code and associated datasets. The Eclipse Foundation's governance model includes contribution guidelines, committer structures, and IP management processes that ensure that the framework and the datasets that support it can be extended and maintained by a wider community of contributors beyond the original consortium. This aspect is part of the proposed 3-year governance model of KuDECO, provided and coordinated by FOR.

The **Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme (IRCEP)**, run through WP7 during the project, generated documented evidence of third-party engagement with CODECO data through challenges and hackathons. The lessons learned from IRCEP — including which datasets attracted the most interest and what barriers to reuse were encountered are documented in D30 (M39) and inform the post-project engagement strategy for the Eclipse KuDECO community.

6.3.3 Compliance with the European Open Science Cloud

CODECO's data is compatible with the EOSC federation through Zenodo's status as an EOSC-endorsed repository and through compliance with DCAT-AP metadata standards as implemented by data.europa.eu. Future uptake of CODECO datasets within EOSC thematic communities, particularly those addressing edge computing, IoT, and smart energy, is facilitated by this compliance and by the multi-repository indexation strategy adopted during the project.

7 Limitations and Recommendations

7.1 Current Limitations

The CODECO datasets represent a genuine and multi-domain open science contribution, but several limitations should be acknowledged by future users:

- **Geographic specificity.** The mobility datasets (P2, i2CAT, Barcelona) capture a specific urban V2X deployment context; the energy datasets (P4, UPM, Madrid) cover four buildings of a single academic campus; the smart buildings datasets (P6, Almende, Netherlands) reflect a specific Crownstone product deployment; and the manufacturing datasets (P5, fortiss, Munich) are limited to a single AMR testbed. Generalisability to different urban morphologies, national energy market structures, building typologies, and factory configurations will require validation in additional deployment environments.
- **Scale of deployment.** As a research project rather than a production deployment, the use-case environments are instrumented at limited scale. Dataset size may constrain the training of very large-scale AI models without data augmentation or transfer learning techniques.
- **Temporal scope.** Data collection spans 2023 to early 2026. As network and infrastructure conditions evolve, particularly with 5G/6G commercial rollout and EU energy market reforms, datasets may require updates to remain representative of operational conditions.
- **Dataset usage statistics.** In figShare and Zenodo, the 13 datasets were published in March 2026, concurrent with project closure. Impact measurement will require a dedicated monitoring period post-publication.

7.2 Follow-up for Maximising Impact

- Elsevier Data in Brief proposal: the CODECO (FOR as Editor) will provide a proposal for an article (data descriptor) in Elsevier “Data in Brief” (May 2026).
- **Analysis of use in the final report.** Zenodo analytics and OpenAIRE tracking will be further detailed in the CODECO final report (May 2026).
- **Engage with EU Industrial Data Spaces.** CODECO's datasets align with the EU Common European Data Spaces initiative across the Manufacturing, Energy, and Mobility data spaces. Engagement with these communities via partners I2CAT, ECL, KuDECO channels can position the datasets as reference contributions within the relevant sectoral data spaces and increase their long-term reuse potential.
- **Extend geographic and temporal coverage through KuDECO.** The Eclipse KuDECO community will be used as the vehicle for soliciting contributions of additional use-case datasets from new deployment environments, progressively addressing the geographic and temporal limitations documented above. Dataset versioning on Zenodo should be used to publish updates without losing traceability to the original CODECO-funded records.

8 Summary

This document is the third and final version of the CODECO Data Management and Ethics Handling deliverable (D4), covering the full project lifespan from January 2023 to March 2026 under Horizon Europe Grant Agreement 101092696.

D4 provides a comprehensive account of how data was collected, curated, managed, and shared across the six CODECO use-cases and the CODECO Experimentation Framework. A total of 13 datasets were produced, covering urban mobility and VRU safety (P2), media delivery and 5G edge telemetry (P3), building-level energy management (P4 and P6), wireless AGV/AMR factory automation (P5), and Kubernetes-based edge-cloud infrastructure metrics (CODEF and CSDG). All datasets are publicly available under CC BY 4.0 licences, with persistent DOIs, across three repositories: the CODECO Eclipse Research GitLab, Zenodo, and figShare.

CODECO's data management practices were aligned throughout with the FAIR principles and the Horizon Europe Open Science requirements. Metadata records, standardised README files, and GDPR-compliant anonymisation procedures were applied consistently to all datasets involving cyber-physical system data. The six-step ethics and PII verification process, coordinated by the CODECO Ethics Committee (ETC), ensured that no personally identifiable information was retained in any open-access deposit. Open science compliance, FAIR implementation, and data reuse practices are documented in Section 3.

The impact of the CODECO datasets spans scientific, technological, and societal and sectoral dimensions, as documented in Section 6. Early engagement data for the 13 datasets, published to Zenodo and figShare in March 2026, is presented in Table 11; longitudinal impact tracking via Zenodo analytics and OpenAIRE is recommended at six-month intervals from mid-2026 onwards. The limitations of the datasets and recommendations for maximising their post-project impact are addressed in Section 7.

The sustainability of data access and community stewardship beyond the project end date is guaranteed through the Eclipse KuDECO open-source project, the long-term data preservation policies of Zenodo and figShare, and indexation within the European open data infrastructure via data.europa.eu and OpenAIRE.

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